

Structure of Faceted Naphthalene-Benzoic Acid Eutectic

P. S. BASSI* and N. K. SHARMA**

Department of Chemistry,

and

K. N. GOSWAMI

Department of Physics, Jammu University, Jammu-180 001

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Microstructure studies of naphthalene-benzoic acid eutectic have shown it to be a faceted-faceted structure in agreement with the recent classification of the eutectics. X-ray studies of the eutectic have shown that certain interplanar distances and the intensities of the reflections in the solidified eutectic differ markedly from those of the pure components, indicating a preferential orientation between the components in the eutectic.

ACCORDING to the classification given by Jackson and Hunt¹, micromorphologies depend on the entropy of fusion of the pure components; the high entropy constituents form an eutectic having irregular (faceted) growth from the melt. Little has been studied about such faceted eutectics² and hence naphthalene-benzoic acid system, in which both the components have a high entropy of fusion, has been chosen for study. Growth kinetics and the structure of the liquid eutectics have also been studied recently³. Hogan⁴ showed a unique crystallographic orientation relationship between constituent phases and their mating planes. Perfect lamellar grains have been found in lamellar Sn-Cd eutectic by Gruzleski and Winegard⁵ but in a number of systems, the eutectic grains do not exhibit a fixed crystal orientation with respect to external lines of forces. Recently, it has been shown that certain frequencies in the ir spectra of naphthalene-benzoic acid eutectic are restricted, showing thereby that there is a specific orientation between the constituents with respect to each other in this composite material⁶. In the present investigation, microscopic, X-ray and D.S.C. studies of naphthalene-benzoic acid eutectic has been made and it has been further established that there is orientation of some of the planes of the new composite formed.

Experimental

Naphthalene (U.S.S.R.) was purified by sublimation and benzoic acid (A.R., B.D.H., London) was taken as such. Purity of naphthalene (m.p. 80.30°) and benzoic acid was checked by the determination of their melting points. Accurately weighed naphthalene and benzoic acid were taken in a tube which was then sealed to avoid evaporation. The material in the tube was melted and then suddenly chilled in ice cold water. This process of melting and chilling was repeated 4-5 times. The tube was then broken and the solid mixture thus formed was

powdered using agate mortar and pestle. The phase diagram of naphthalene-benzoic acid system was determined by thaw point method. Eutectic was formed at 0.667 mole fraction of naphthalene with its eutectic point at 69.1°. The accuracy in determining the eutectic point was $\pm 0.1^\circ$.

A small amount of the eutectic or that of the pure components was taken on a clean glass slide and carefully melted. A cover slip was then glided over it. These glass slides were then observed under microscope. The heat of fusion of the eutectic and the pure components were determined using differential scanning calorimeter, DSC IB, Perkin Elmer, USA in N₂ atmosphere. These were found to be 32.2, 33.4 and 29.4 cal/g for naphthalene, benzoic acid and the eutectic, respectively.

The X-ray analysis of the eutectic and the pure components was carried out by powder method using Debye Scherrer camera with nickel filtered copper (K α) radiation. The intensities of X-ray lines were determined by visual comparison of the lines with the standard intensity scale which had been prepared previously.

Results and Discussion

(a) *Microscopic and D.S.C. studies*: Hunt and Jackson⁷ argued that the type of growth of an eutectic depends upon a factor α . Non-faceted growth occurs when $\alpha < 2$, whereas faceted growth occurs when $\alpha > 2$.

$$\alpha = \xi \frac{\Delta S_f}{R}$$

where $\Delta S_f/R$ is the entropy of fusion in dimensionless units and ξ is a crystallographic factor depending upon the geometry of the molecule and is less than or almost equal to one. Benzoic acid and naphthalene have $\Delta S_f/R$ values of 5.25 and 6.45, respectively (ΔS_f values were calculated from the heat of fusion values at the melting points⁸).

* Department of Chemistry, Guru Nanak Dev University, Amritsar-143 005.

** Author for correspondence.

Hence growth of naphthalene and benzoic acid should be faceted. The values of heat of fusion obtained from D.S.C. agree with the theoretical values within the error range. Experimental values of $\Delta S_f/R$ were found to be 5.91, 5.17 and 5.49 for naphthalene, benzoic acid and the eutectic, respectively. Higher values of $\Delta S_f/R$ indicate that the eutectic is faceted-faceted type. When the growth of the eutectic was observed in the glass slide under a microscope with suitable magnification, it was seen that the growth was irregular (faceted) in agreement with the recent classification of the eutectics⁷. Not much literature is available on the studies of faceted-faceted eutectics.

(b) *X-ray studies*: From X-ray photographs of the eutectic, naphthalene and benzoic acid, it is clear that there is a marked difference in the interplanar distances and the relative intensities of the composite material and the individual components. From the study of X-ray photographs, the following are evident:

1. A number of X-ray reflections on the X-ray photographs indicate that the eutectic is crystalline in nature.
2. There is a rapid fall in the value of intensity of reflections as a function of the diffraction angle $\frac{\sin \theta}{\lambda}$.

From the study of Table 1, the following characteristic features have been observed. In eutectic, the reflections with interplanar spacing $d \approx 3.65, 3.42, 2.93, 2.52$ and $2.27 \text{ \AA}$ have relatively stronger intensities as compared to the similar lines found in benzoic acid and naphthalene. From the above observation, it is inferred that the X-ray diffraction pattern of the eutectic is different from that of the individual components constituting it. In other words, the X-ray photographs of the pure components cannot be exactly superimposed on the photographs of the eutectic composite. Some of the reflections as mentioned above show deviations in the intensity and in interplanar spacings.

It can be inferred from these observations that the eutectic is not only a pure mechanical mixture of two components, but there is orientation of some atomic planes in the composite. Such an observation has also been made by ir studies⁸.

The rapid fall in the intensity of reflections can be attributed to various reasons. There may be some disorder in the location of atoms forming the composite. It can also be due to thermal vibration of atoms making the composite. It is the thermal activation of the interaction of the two components which is responsible for the formation of the eutectic. As a confirmation of this effect it is found that reflections are slightly diffused in intensity.

TABLE I

Naphthalene		Eutectic		Benzoic acid	
d/Å	R.I.	d/Å	R.I.	d/Å	R.I.
—	—	10.84	s	10.90	s
7.28	m	7.28	w	—	—
5.78	w	—	—	—	—
5.62	w	—	—	—	—
—	—	5.42	w	5.43	m
—	—	5.12	vs	5.15	vs
4.65	m	—	—	—	—
—	—	4.68	w	4.63	mw
4.50	vs	4.50	w	—	—
4.12	m	4.18	w	—	—
4.11	w	4.10	w	—	—
3.70	vw	3.71	s	3.71	s
3.64	vw	3.65	s	—	—
—	—	—	—	3.62	w
—	—	—	—	3.50	w
3.51	vw	—	—	—	—
3.48	w	3.48	w	—	—
—	—	3.42	vs	3.42	s
3.38	mw	3.38	m	—	—
3.21	w	3.19	s	3.19	m
3.00	w	2.99	w	—	—
—	—	2.98	s	2.95	mw
2.80	vw	—	—	—	—
2.76	vw	—	—	—	—
—	—	—	—	2.72	vw
—	—	2.66	vw	2.56	vw
2.55	vw	2.52	mw	—	—
2.43	vw	2.43	vw	—	—
—	—	2.42	vw	—	—
2.28	vw	2.27	mw	—	—
—	—	2.09	mw	2.09	vw
1.84	w	1.90	mw	1.91	vw
1.82	w	—	—	—	—
1.81	w	—	—	—	—
—	—	1.61	vw	—	—
—	—	1.58	vw	—	—

The classification of the relative intensity of lines is based on the following criteria: vs=80-100; s=60-80; m=40-60; mw=20-40; w=10-20 and vw=0-10.

It can thus be concluded that X-ray studies indicate a sort of preferential ordering of atoms making an eutectic.

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